

An Ocean Practices Maturity Model: from Good to Best Practices

1 **Carlo Mantovani¹, Jay Pearlman², Anna Rubio³, Rachel Przeslawski⁴, Mark Bushnell⁵, Pauline**
2 **Simpson⁶, Lorenzo Corgnati¹, Enrique Alvarez⁷, Simone Cosoli⁸, Hugh Roarty⁹**

3 ¹ Institute of Marine Sciences, National Research Council of Italy, Lerici, Italy

4 ² Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, Paris, France

5 ³ AZTI, Marine Research, Basque Research and Technology Alliance, (BRTA), Pasaia, Spain

6 ⁴ NSW Department of Primary Industries, Fisheries, Huskisson, NSW, Australia

7 ⁵ CoastalObsTechServices LLC, Virginia Beach, VA, United States of America

8 ⁶ UNESCO -IOC Project Office for IODE, Oostende, Belgium

9 ⁷ OceanPrediction Decade Collaborative Center - Mercator Ocean International, Toulouse, France

10 ⁸ University of Western Australia, 35 Stirling Hwy, Crawley WA 6009

11 ⁹ Department of Marine and Coastal Sciences, Rutgers, The State University of New Jersey, New
12 Brunswick, NJ, United States of America

13 * Correspondence:

14 Carlo Mantovani
15 carlo.mantovani@cnr.it

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18 Abstract

19 Ocean practices, intended as a wide spectrum of methodologies supporting ocean-related research,
20 operations, and applications, are constantly developed and improved to enable informed decision-
21 making. Practices start from the idea of an individual or a group and often evolve towards what can be
22 called good or best practices. This bottom-up approach may in principle result in different paths for the
23 evolution of each practice, and ultimately generate situations where it is not clear to a new user how to
24 compare two practices aiming at the same objective, and determine which one is best. Also, although
25 a best practice is supposed to be the result of a multi-institutional collaborative effort based on the
26 principles of evidence, repeatability and comparability, a set of individual requirements is not yet
27 defined in literature for a practice to be considered a good, better, and ultimately a best practice. This
28 paper proposes a method for addressing those questions and presents a new maturity model for ocean
29 practices, built upon existing maturity models for systems and software, developed and adopted in the
30 last decades. The model provides attributes for assessing both the maturity of the practice description
31 and its implementation. It also provides a framework for analyzing gaps and suggesting actions for
32 practice evolution. The model has been tested against a series of widely adopted practices and the

33 results are reported and discussed. This work facilitates a common approach for developing and
34 assessing practices, from which greater interoperability and trust can be achieved.

35 **1 Introduction**

36 *A best practice has been defined as a “methodology that has repeatedly produced superior results*
37 *relative to other methodologies with the same objective; to be fully elevated to a best practice, a*
38 *promising method will have been adopted and employed by multiple organizations”* (Pearlman et al.,
39 2019).

40 Best practices provide significant benefits, and the use of shared and well-documented methods support
41 global and regional interoperability across the value chain, from requirement setting, through
42 observations, to data management and ultimately to the end user applications and societal impacts
43 (Figure 1-1). By offering transparency, best practices engender trust in data and information. They
44 facilitate capacity development through their documentation. They further maintain provenance for
45 data and information.

46 Formally defined, documented practices should ensure that people knowledgeable in the field can
47 successfully execute the practice and have the same outcomes that the process creators achieved. As a
48 practice matures, broader adoption will test the practice in many environments to ascertain the
49 applicability to diverse regional missions where, for example, low-cost solutions may be required.

50 In formulating a maturity model for ocean practices, key questions should be addressed as a practice
51 matures: which method can be considered a best practice, and is there a measure of maturity to identify
52 best practices? Does the process described in the practice follow guidelines or standards produced by
53 experts? Is the documentation easily findable and allow easy readability? Is the practice documentation
54 format consistent with machine-to-machine discoverability? Has the practice been reviewed by
55 independent experts? (Horstmann et al., 2020). For operational systems, questions relating to long term
56 implementation should also be addressed (Mantovani et al., 2023).

57 This paper focuses on the maturity characteristics of a practice, both its implementation and its
58 documentation. It addresses the above questions and forms a new maturity model identifying the
59 attributes which enable a practice to become a good, better or best practice. The existence of a
60 sufficiently detailed maturity model is beneficial in many ways. A maturity model will be a guide for
61 practices to enable users to choose a more mature practice. For new (or reluctant) users, a better practice
62 has documentation that is sufficient for consistent replication. If the document structure and related
63 metadata follow a standard format, users can more easily compare practices. Users will know what is
64 needed to implement a practice or if there are quality assurance procedures when using a practice. For
65 mature practices, user feedback mechanisms will also help with selection. For practice developers, the
66 maturity model offers clear guidelines for continuous improvement of practices. It can foster inter-
67 institutional and international collaboration toward practice standardization.

68 The ocean-focused model derives from work over many decades on defining the maturity of space
69 systems, software development and, more recently, project management. These are presented in the
70 next section 2. The new maturity model is presented in section 3. Then, in section 4, the maturity model
71 is evaluated through application to three case studies: High Frequency Radar (HFR), Multibeam ocean
72 floor monitoring and quality assurance for sea level observations. An assessment is also carried out for
73 current GOOS/OBPS-endorsed practices.

74 **2 Existing Practice Maturity Models**

75 For a maturity model to be of continuing value, certain tradeoffs should be considered. For example,
76 if a model is general, it can last without review for a long time, but it does not provide very specific
77 guidelines for evaluating and evolving a practice. On the other hand, specific criteria can provide
78 guidance for evolving practices, but they should be reviewed regularly in order to keep up with
79 technology evolution. Practices across disciplines can vary and a maturity model may not be
80 appropriate for all practices if the level descriptions are too specific. A summary of the benefits and
81 challenges is provided in Table 2-1.

82 Maturity models usually comprise three or more levels of maturity from initial concept to a fully mature
83 practice. The ocean community currently uses three level maturity models. The *Framework for Ocean*
84 *Observing* (FOO) (Lindstrom et al., 2012) and the Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS)
85 (OceanBestPractices System, 2024) each has three levels. For the OBPS, these are:

86 **Concept:** A practice is being developed at one institution(s) but has not been agreed to by the
87 community; requirements and form for a methodology are understood (but practice may not be
88 documented).

89 **Pilot or Demonstrated:** Practice is being demonstrated and validated; limited consensus exists on
90 widespread use or in any given situation.

91 **Mature:** Practice is well demonstrated for a given objective, documented and peer reviewed; practice
92 is commonly used by more than one organization.

93 While the three levels represent a logical progression of maturity, their description does not provide
94 enough detail to accurately identify the appropriate level for a practice. It is unclear at what point a
95 practice becomes a good practice or even a better practice. The three-level maturity scale is also focused
96 on the practice itself, but does not account for aspects such as training, user feedback, routine updates,
97 nor guidance on how to write and make available practice documentation.

98 In project management, software development and system development, the number of levels typically
99 range between four and nine. For long term projects that are complex, include many different teams
100 and last one or more decades, maturity models with more levels may be used. NASA ran complex
101 space system developments, monitoring technology from inception to space flight hardware over
102 decades. They used a nine level Technology Readiness Level maturity model (Hirshorn and Jefferies,
103 2016). Similarly, NOAA has a nine level system as an idea evolves to a mature system (NOAA, 2019)

104 Experience developing and using maturity models in industry and academia suggests that a five level
105 structure may be optimum for most applications (Chrissis et al., 2011). Maturity models are broadly
106 used in industry. They cover a wide range of subject areas where they are used to monitor the efficiency
107 of business processes (Tarhan et al., 2016; Lutkevich, 2024) such as project management (Pennypacker
108 and Grant, 2002; Rosenstock et al., 2000) or software development (ISO/IEC 15504). The models have
109 several objectives: benchmark internal performance; catalyze performance improvements; and create
110 and evolve a common language to understand performance. The latter supports a commitment to foster
111 the engagement of all stakeholders. The degree of maturity described in these business models is done
112 through assigning levels related to the degree to which processes are documented and followed
113 (Newsom, 2024).

114 For software development, there are complementary paths for assessing maturity, e.g. International
115 Standards Organization (ISO) 9001 standards (ISO 9001:2015, 2024) or the Capability Maturity Model
116 (CMM) (Lutkevich, 2024). The main difference between CMM and ISO 9001 lies in their respective

117 purposes: ISO 9001 specifies a minimal acceptable quality level for software processes, while CMM
118 establishes a framework for continuous process improvement. ISO in collaboration with the
119 International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) has also provided a series of guidelines known as the
120 Software Process Improvement and Capability Determination (SPICE) framework (ISO/IEC 15504).
121 CMM is more explicit than the ISO standard in defining the means to be employed. For its
122 implementation, the CMM describes a five-level evolutionary path of increasingly organized and
123 systematically more mature processes (Figure 2-1), (Lutkevich, 2024). IOOS chose a five-level model
124 in their 2010 blueprint for full capability (U.S, IOOS Office, 2010).

125 The ocean maturity model defined in this paper also uses five levels. Five levels offer a granularity that
126 has enough detail to differentiate between maturity levels without being overly intricate. The five
127 levels, with appropriate sublevels, allow organizations to identify areas to focus their efforts for
128 improvement.

129 **3 A New Ocean Practices Maturity Model**

130 A key question to be considered in designing an ocean-focused five level maturity model is how can
131 the five levels be formulated to stimulate evolution from a practice to an endorsed, widely-adopted best
132 practice. The description of levels in Figure 2-1 for software evolution provides a foundation. For
133 oceans, levels one and two are similar to the software model and are focused on taking ad hoc practice
134 of level 1 and moving it toward a repeatable practice (Level 2). In Level 3, practices should be open,
135 defined and fully documented so they can be replicated by other experts. At Level 4, the practices are
136 well developed and adopted across multiple institutions. Level 5 includes mature practices which are
137 even more widely implemented, have user feedback and are endorsed by experts. Figure 3-1 offers a
138 very high level sketch of what each level is. This would not suffice by itself. More details at each level
139 are necessary and are provided in Section 3.1 below.

140 **3.1 Ocean Practices Maturity Model Attributes**

141 The maturity model levels described above have been expanded in a number of attributes that are
142 inspired by four foundational elements. First is multi-institutional adoption and use of the practice.
143 Second is complete and open documentation of the practice including the process description and
144 related metadata. The documentation should be in a sustained repository. Third is community
145 engagement and feedback in evolving and endorsing the practice. Fourth is sustaining the practice and
146 its related experience. This would involve, for example, training in its use and updates relevant to
147 changing technologies.

148 There are two parallel processes included in maturity assessments. First is the maturity of a practice
149 and its documentation. The second is the maturity of the implementation of the practice, particularly
150 for operational systems. Both the practice maturity and the implementation maturity are considered in
151 building the maturity model. The new ocean maturity model described in this paper is designed to
152 support diverse elements of the ocean value chain, which includes observations, modeling and
153 applications. It strikes a balance so that enough detail is included to support practice evolution while
154 still offering criteria general enough to keep the maturity model stable and valid over time. For best
155 practices to evolve, tools to monitor implementation are needed as well as feedback loops with users
156 (Przeslawski et al., 2021). Ideally, there is a central repository which collects feedback information,
157 supports optimization and keeps track of the evolution. The evolution of practice maturity is promoted
158 at all levels. The implementation maturity is visible only in levels four and five when the practice is
159 mature enough to be considered for an operational or complex research environment. For example,
160 Level 5 in Table 3-1 includes user feedback loops, diagnostic tools and protocols for evolution.

161 In defining the attributes for each level, there are many trade-offs about what constitutes a good, better
162 or best practice. Applying these maturity assessment criteria to practices is a combination of fact and
163 judgment. In defining the attributes of each level, there was a focused effort to make as many of them
164 quantitative and to minimize subjective judgements. Additionally, in some cases, two similar attributes
165 are assigned to two different levels. In this case, at the higher level, the attribute is more formal in its
166 structure or more pervasive in its use. For example, in Level 4, a practice is used by multiple institutions
167 while in Level 5, the practice is adopted at least regionally. Similarly, in Level 4 a practice document
168 describes how practitioners can verify their successful implementation of the practice, while in Level
169 5 implementation of practice has formal tools to accomplish this task.

170 Level 5 introduces endorsement. To guide users in method selection, an endorsement process was
171 developed through a collaboration of the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) and OBPS which
172 provides guidelines for endorsement (Hermes (ed.), 2020; Przeslawski et al., 2023). Based on this
173 experience, OBPS has defined an endorsement process that can be extended to a broader range of
174 disciplines (Bushnell and Pearlman (eds), 2024). An example of an endorsed practice is the Ocean
175 Gliders Oxygen SOP V1. (Lopez-Garcia et al., 2023)

176 In applying labels to levels four and five, it is recognized that better or best could be relative to a
177 specific environment. A better practice for the coastal regions and a better practice in open ocean may
178 be best for their locations, but may differ in their description and implementation. Thus, multiple
179 practices may exist simultaneously for the same high level objective. For example, measurements of
180 dissolved oxygen in seawater are quite commonly used by biologists as a measure of water quality.
181 Low oxygen levels stress organisms and anoxic conditions create dead zones. Oxygen levels are also
182 used by physical oceanographers as water mass tracers to estimate how much time has passed since
183 deep water was last in contact with the atmosphere, requiring measurements with a higher accuracy.
184 To make the measurements, a wide variety of practices may be employed, each with benefits and
185 drawbacks. It is best to modify the traditional titrimetric method used in open ocean waters when
186 making the same measurement in coastal waters with high organic loads (American Public Health
187 Association, 1976).

188 **3.2 Ocean Practices Maturity Model Assessment**

189 Assignment of maturity level for a process must be transparent and be easily used by those employing
190 the maturity model as a tool for self-assessing the maturity of their practice. It must also allow
191 straightforward interpretation by users who want to decide whether to adopt a practice. To this end, a
192 quantitative scoring system was defined for assessing a practice. The score for a level is built on
193 specific scores for each attribute of that level, so that the sum is the number “one”. This is valid for all
194 the levels. While the assignment of “one” as the sum is arbitrary, it makes the assessment within and
195 across levels more straightforward. Another factor in the scoring is that a weighting is introduced to
196 recognize that not all attributes at a given level are equally important when progressing to a good, better
197 or best practice. This was done assigning non-uniform scores to attributes, within each level. Attribute
198 scores, thus their priority rating within each level, are based on the authors’ experience and inputs from
199 other experts in the ocean community. Since the number of attributes is not the same for each level,
200 but their score has to sum one within each level, individual attribute scores from different levels are
201 not meant to be comparable, i.e. a concept of absolute priority is not defined.

202 Using this scoring, the calculation of the maturity level for a practice looks at the items needed to
203 achieve each level (see Table 3-1) and follows a few simple rules. To be awarded as fully compliant
204 with a level, a score of 1.0 is required in that level (i.e. all the attributes are fulfilled in that level).

205 However, there will be times in the evolution of a practice when not all of the attributes to achieve a
206 level have been satisfied, and at the same time attributes from the next higher levels have been satisfied.
207 To not restrict developers, the score for a level can be obtained as the sum of all the scores of the
208 fulfilled criteria for that level and the one above it. There is an additional facet that to be declared at a
209 certain level, all items in the lower levels must be completed. Synthesizing this approach in other
210 words, maturity Level N is obviously achieved when all attributes are fulfilled from Level 1 to N. In a
211 more realistic case in which not all the levels are fully completed, Level N can be achieved when: a)
212 all the attributes from levels from 1 to N-1 are fully satisfied and b) attributes fulfilled in Level N and
213 Level N+1 give a score ≥ 1 . Levels N+2 and above cannot contribute to an additional score, in order
214 to encourage a balanced evolution of the practice.

215 For an example of the assessment calculation see table 3-2. The table considers a practice that has
216 completed Level 2 and is working toward recognition at Level 3. It has satisfied three of four attributes
217 for Level 3 and has a score of 0.70, but does not yet have a score of 1.00 at Level 3. However, it may
218 use actions from Level 4 that it has completed to get credit toward Level 3 completion, but it cannot
219 use any activities from two levels higher, in this case, Level 5. In the case of Table 3-2, three attributes
220 of Level 4 are satisfied: the practice document describes how practitioners can verify their successful
221 implementation of the practice, the practice has been submitted to a sustained repository in a
222 standardized format, and practice documents and metadata are machine-readable, which together have
223 an associated score of 0.35. Adding this to the 0.70 from Level 3 attributes that are satisfied, gives a
224 total score of 1.05 and the practice is acknowledged to be at Level 3, a “good practice”. It is also
225 necessary that all items at lower levels (in this case Levels 1 and 2) have been fully completed so that
226 there are no residual holes in the maturity evolution. The rationale for not using scores from two levels
227 above the current level is to focus the maturity evolution at no more than two levels and not have an
228 effort distributed across the entire maturity spectrum. This helps users more clearly understand if a
229 practice is good, better or best.

230 In order to consider the full capability of a practice in terms of readiness for each level and to provide
231 a quick visual and complementary reference for users of the scoring results above, a practice can be
232 assigned from one to five stars corresponding to its maturity level attributes. The number of full stars
233 indicates that a specific level has been completed. Half stars may be used for completion of a partial
234 level. Since this is a qualitative score, a half star does not mean the achievement of a score of 0.50 in
235 that level; it means that some score was achieved in that Level. A qualitative score of 5 stars is equal
236 to the quantitative score of 5.00, meaning that the practice is a “Best Practice” and has fulfilled all
237 attributes in the maturity model. The quantitative score and the number of stars may change as the
238 practice matures. Specific examples of this scoring system are given in the next section where
239 documented practices related to three ocean observing practices are considered, and the maturity
240 assessment is done.

241 **4 Application of the Maturity Assessment**

242 In this section, three practices are provided and analyzed to understand how the maturity scale is
243 applied. These include practices related to different ocean observing technologies and methodologies:
244 High Frequency Radar (HFR), a multi-beam scanner and a sea level quality control process. While
245 these are all observations, they represent various segments of ocean observing. In addition, interviews
246 were conducted with lead authors on seven OBPS/GOOS endorsed practices to consider whether these
247 practices are good, better or best practices. A summary of the lead author self-assessment from the
248 interviews, giving the maturity rating, is provided in section 4.4.

249 All the exemplars in this section 4 have completed the attributes of Level 1, 2 and 3, and therefore have
250 a guaranteed starting score of 3 (and 3 full stars). Thus, the discussions and tables below focus on Level
251 4 and 5. For the three examples of HFR, multi-beam scanner and sea level quality control, the maturity
252 tables include comments on each attribute to better understand how the factors are applied in the
253 ratings.

254 **4.1 Assessment of High Frequency Radar (HFR) Practices**

255 **What is HFR?**

256 In oceanography, HFR is a remote sensing technology employed for monitoring ocean surface currents,
257 waves, and wind direction. Operating in the HF radio frequency band (3-30 MHz), these radar systems
258 extract ocean surface current velocity information from the Doppler shift induced by the movement of
259 the ocean surface (Reyes et al., 2022; Lorente et al., 2022; Gurgel et al., 1999; Gurgel, 1994). They are
260 typically deployed in networks along coastlines, providing information in extended coastal zones and
261 up to 200 km from the shoreline.

262 **What issue in ocean observing is it addressing?**

263 HR radars are complementary to other existing instruments used in oceanography for monitoring ocean
264 currents and waves. Traditional oceanographic methods often involve deploying buoys or drifters, or
265 moored Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCs or ADCPs). More conventional instrumentation
266 can be limited in spatial and/or temporal coverage and may not provide real-time data, and do not
267 sample the upper layer of the water column where the ocean-atmosphere exchanges are most
268 pronounced. HFRs provides non-intrusive, wide-area coverage of coastal regions, offering real-time
269 data at high spatial and temporal resolution from an easily accessible shore location. Their primary
270 output is a 2-dimensional map of ocean surface currents. Gridded or single-point waves (significant
271 wave height, period, direction) and wind (direction) data can be derived also (Roarty, et al., 2019a).

272 **What are the challenges?**

273 Challenges of HFR technology and related research activities are multiple and are synthesized in recent
274 papers (Roarty, et al., 2019b; Rubio et al., 2017; Lorente, et al., 2022; Reyes, et al., 2022; de Vos, et
275 al., 2020). Given the multiple applications in operational oceanography, a priority identified by the
276 research community was the efficient and standardized management of near real time HFR-derived
277 velocity maps. To obtain surface current vectors, an HFR installation must include at least two radar
278 sites, each one measuring the radial velocity component in its look direction when operated in standard
279 monostatic configuration. Different sources of uncertainty in the velocity estimation can be related to
280 variations of the radial current component within the radar scattering patch or over the duration of the
281 radar measurement; incorrect antenna patterns or errors in empirical first order line determination, the
282 presence of environmental noise (Rubio et al., 2017). Also, in the combination from radials additional
283 geometric errors can affect the accuracy of the HFR data, like the Geometric Dilution Of Precision
284 (GDOP), (Chapman et al.,1997).

285 The need of ensuring best data quality for near-real time (NRT) data products motivated the community
286 to work on the definition of a practice including the most suited QA/QC protocols, based on metrics
287 which could be computed, with a reasonable computational effort, directly from the received data and
288 a set of reference threshold values.

289 **What is the maturity of the HFR practices?**

290 Two practices related to HFR technology are analyzed in this section. They both refer to Quality
291 Control of HFR data and have been developed in two different regions, Europe and Australia.

292 A first practice is selected from the Joint European Research Infrastructure for Coastal Observatories
293 (JERICO) inventory: Recommendation Report 2 on improved common procedures for HFR QC
294 analysis, JERICO-NEXT Deliverable 5.14, Version 2.0. (Corgnati et al., 2024).

295 In 2014, EuroGOOS initiated the HFR Task Team to advance the establishment of an operational HFR
296 network in Europe. The focus was on coordinated data management and integrating basic products into
297 major marine data distribution platforms. A core group of this task team was then involved in a series
298 of projects (Lorente, et al., 2022) that supported the development of practices for HFR system
299 operations including surface currents data management.

300 The project deliverable JERICO-NEXT D5.14 is the practice describing the data model to be applied
301 to HFR derived surface current data required for complying with international standards. This
302 document, which is available from the OBPS, illustrates the practice maturity which relies on standards
303 (NetCDF data format, CF conventions, INSPIRE directives) and widely accepted procedures
304 (QARTOD manual, US HFR network best practices), and has been drafted in the multi-institutional
305 context mentioned above.

306 A second practice is selected from the Ocean Radar Facility at the University of Western Australia
307 (UWA) (Cosoli and Grcic, 2024; de Vos, et al., 2020). The practice is also provided in the oBPS
308 repository. The Ocean Radar Facility at the University of Western Australia (UWA) is part of
309 Australia's Integrated Marine Observing System (IMOS) and was first established in 2009. Best
310 practices and workflows were established in collaboration with the Australian Ocean Data Network
311 (AODN) to document near real-time (NRT) and delayed-mode (DM) data flow, planning, clarify
312 responsibilities, improve communication, ensure transparency, and aid in deployment reporting. These
313 are refreshed periodically to reflect changes in network settings and hardware or software upgrades.
314 Standard practices include using near-surface currents from independent platforms to optimize radar
315 settings and assess QA/QC tests quantitatively. Optimized thresholds are then established based on
316 regional variability in current regimes for both near real-time and delayed mode products rather than
317 being set a-priori.

318 Maturity of the Practices associated with each of these HFR applications are assessed. The different
319 levels of maturity associated with these practices (Level 4 and Level 5) are detailed in Table 4-1.

320 Level 4: for (Corgnati et al., 2024) attributes of level 4 are fully satisfied. In particular, thanks to the
321 commitment of the EuroGOOS HFR Task Team and its operational asset, the European HFR Node
322 (EU HFR Node), in promoting the multi-institutional adoption and implementation of the European
323 QC, data and metadata model for real-time HFR data, specific procedures for regularly reviewing and
324 updating the data model practice documentation, for providing feedback loops with users, for providing
325 training on the data model application and for providing means for assessing the correct adoption of
326 the data model are in place and described in the practice documentation. The EU HFR Node also
327 provides an operational service for collecting HFR data, quality checking and converting them
328 according to the QC and data model: this workflow operationally checks adherence to file format
329 conventions and metadata in the NRT and DM pipelines.

330 (Cosoli and Grcic, 2024) reported that all Level 4 attributes are met, however acknowledging that
331 advanced skill levels may be required to replicate some of the proposed tests and approaches. Feedback
332 loops are received directly from the data users when inconsistencies are noted in the data products or

333 clarification about data formats and content are needed. Also, the data collection center (Australian
334 Ocean Data Network, AODN) operationally checks adherence to file format conventions and metadata
335 in their NRT and DM pipelines. AODN also ensures the Ocean Radar Facility satisfies standard IMOS
336 community practices.

337 Level 5: for (Corgnati et al., 2024) attributes of level 5 are partially satisfied (5 out of 6). The
338 aforementioned commitment and operational service provided by the EuroGOOS HFR Task Team and
339 the EU HFR Node promote the global adoption of the practice and support its evolution. The missing
340 attribute relates to the formal endorsement of the practice. This step is still being implemented.

341 (Cosoli and Grcic, 2024) report that 5 out of 6 level 5 attributes are met, however consensus is reached
342 in regards to the fundamental need of thorough review and endorsement.

343 The comparison is included here as another potential for using the maturity model. If there are similar
344 practices with the same objective, there is interest in assessing if convergence between the practices
345 into a single practice can be achieved. The parties (Corgnati et al., 2024; Cosoli and Grcic, 2024) have
346 agreed to pursue this as the maturity of both practices is nearly the same. The convergence effort was
347 motivated by the maturity model analyses of this use case and envisions an investigation for other
348 practices adopted in the same field, e.g. the QARTOD manual for HFR data QC (U.S.Integrated Ocean
349 Observing System, 2022b), aiming at the production of a unique and endorsed reference practice for
350 the international HFR community. The subject of convergence will be further discussed in a dedicated
351 future document. Also, the dialogue will be extended to other national and regional HFR networks
352 (Roarty et al, 2019, Jena et al., 2019) aiming at a global HFR practices harmonization and maturity
353 model application.

354 **4.2 Assessment of Multibeam Practice**

355 Multibeam echosounders are marine acoustic systems that create data based on the interaction between
356 underwater sound waves and physical obstacles, the latter of which can either be on the seabed or in
357 the water column. Data acquisition involves a transmitter which emits multiple sound pulses at a given
358 time and a receiver which receives this sound pulse. The difference in time between the send and
359 receive signal will result in a depth measurement (bathymetry), and the strength of the return of the
360 emitted pulse can be used to infer seabed hardness (backscatter). The main use of multibeam
361 echosounders is to generate high resolution maps of the physical features of the seafloor over a broad
362 spatial area. These maps can then be used for a range of purposes , including characterizing key seabed
363 features (Post et al., 2022, Wakeford et al., 2023), choosing benthic sampling locations (Bax and
364 Williams, 2001), and producing habitat maps (Miisiuk and Brown, 2024). Acoustic techniques can also
365 be used to detect and predict the spatial extent of broad ecological communities such as kelp and sessile
366 invertebrates (Rattray et al., 2013, Bridge et al., 2020). All of these contribute to establishment and
367 management of marine parks (Lucieer et al 2024). Occasionally multibeam is used to detect change
368 based on data acquired from repeated surveys (Rattray et al., 2013).

369 Until recently, multibeam practices were not unified or publicly accessible, making it challenging to
370 collate and compare data from different surveys particularly in relation to characterizing and managing
371 Australia's vast marine park network (Przeslawski et al., 2019). The current version of the Australian
372 Multibeam Guidelines was released in 2020 as a national best practice to guide multibeam data
373 collection, processing and distribution (Picard et al., 2020). This version has higher maturity, than
374 previous iterations, thus providing a useful example for the entire maturity assessment framework
375 described in Table 3-1 above:

- 376 ● Level 1-2: Prior to 2018, the multibeam practices used within Australia were separately
377 developed and internally documented among relevant institutions. Practitioners were unable to
378 discover most of these in-house practices, and each was written for various purposes (e.g.
379 research and monitoring, hydrographic charting) and to varying levels of detail.
- 380 ● Level 3: In 2018, national multibeam guidelines were independently released by two different
381 consortiums, AusSeabed and the NESP Marine Biodiversity Hub (Przeslawski et al., 2019),
382 each of which represented multiple institutions. The practices were released and promoted, and
383 they were lodged on national government webpages, as well as the OBPS Repository.
- 384 ● Level 4: In 2020, the previous two guidelines were merged into a new version and released as
385 part of the national marine sampling best practices for Australian waters (Przeslawski et al.,
386 2023). This version began to be adopted by multiple institutions in Australia (e.g. Geoscience
387 Australia, CSIRO, Australian Hydrographic Office), with rapidly increasing uptake and impact.
- 388 ● Level 4+: By 2024, the Australian Multibeam Guidelines were broadly used throughout
389 Australia as a best practice for seabed mapping and hydrographic mapping. Their maintenance
390 is the responsibility of the AusSeabed Steering Committee, and various related training and
391 data tools are available through (AusSeabed, 2024). The Australian Government recommends
392 them in their permit applications for marine park monitoring and research. Formal endorsement
393 will be sought by the OBPS process established in 2024 (Bushnell and Pearlman, 2024). When
394 this is completed, the guidelines will be at Level 5 maturity.

395 **4.3 Assessment of QARTOD Real-Time Water Level Quality Control Practice**

396 **Why Observe and Disseminate Water Levels in Real-Time?**

397 Water levels are measured using a variety of technologies. Examples include pressure sensors, acoustic
398 rangefinders (guided or unguided), floats / encoder systems, and more recently microwave
399 rangefinders. Applications requiring ever-decreasing latencies have only increased with the need for
400 dissemination in real-time. These include support for safe and efficient maritime commerce, storm
401 surge and inundation observations, and even tsunami observations. (Edwing, 2019) reports the
402 economic benefits of real-time observations, including sea level observations provided each six
403 minutes, are on the order of \$10M per year, while accidents are substantially reduced.

404 **What are the Challenges Associated with Real-Time Water Level Observations?**

405 *“It seems a very simple task to make correct tidal observations; but in my experience, I have found no*
406 *observations which require such constant care and attention...” - Alexander Dallas Bache, Second*
407 *Superintendent of the Coast Survey, 1854*

408 Flaws often detected in real-time include data spikes, invariant flat line, abrupt offsets/shifts, telemetry
409 dropouts, and other equipment failures. Real-time QC can decrease down time and reduce repair costs
410 by alerting operators to data flaws more quickly and assisting with troubleshooting. Other flaws seen
411 in water level data, such as slow sensor drift, platform subsidence, and errors associated with
412 biofouling, cannot be detected in real time.

413 **What is QARTOD?**

414 The Quality Assurance / Quality Control of Real-Time Oceanographic Data (QARTOD) project began
415 as a grassroots effort in 2003. Approximately 75 oceanographers and data managers met at NOAA's
416 National Data Buoy Center to initiate an effort to standardize the quality control of a variety of
417 observations. Several years later, the first manuals were drafted, but there was no authority ready to
418 accept them. In 2013, the U.S. Integrated Ocean Observing System (U.S. IOOS[®], 2010) programme
419 adopted the QARTOD project. Today a total of thirteen manuals (U.S. Integrated Ocean Observing
420 System, 2022a) have been created and endorsed by IOOS.

421 Rigorous community input is the key to the creation of a QARTOD manual. Initially a small committee
422 of subject matter experts (SME) produces the first draft, which is then reviewed by a larger group of
423 users. The edited draft is then reviewed again by all relevant IOOS partners National Oceanic and
424 Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE), Environmental
425 Protection Agency (EPA) , etc. The resultant draft is further reviewed by international agencies with
426 interest in the effort, and then the initial SME committee provides a final review. The manual is
427 submitted to IOOS for acceptance and signed by the Director of IOOS. The manual is posted to the
428 IOOS web site and submitted to both the NOAA Institutional Repository and the OBPS repository.
429 Throughout this process, an adjudication matrix is maintained to record comments and responses. The
430 manuals are updated periodically to ensure that they remain relevant, accurate, and incorporate
431 emergent QC capabilities. This QARTOD process is fully described in the *QARTOD Project Plan*
432 *Update 2022-2026*, (U.S. Integrated Ocean Observing System, 2022a) and in *Prospects for Real-Time*
433 *Quality Control Manuals, How to Create Them, and a Vision for Advanced Implementation* (U.S.
434 Integrated Ocean Observing System, 2020)

435 The practices described in the manuals have been incorporated internationally by governmental and
436 private sector entities. They have also been used in the classroom by graduate-level programmes. The
437 manuals are intended to provide guidance to a broad variety of observers and capabilities. Each manual
438 describes a series of increasingly challenging tests, identified as either required, recommended, and
439 suggested, thus allowing for a variety of data management capabilities to participate in real-time quality
440 control.

441 Initially, the target audience for the QC manuals was the eleven IOOS Regional Associations (RA),
442 which cover the entire coast of the US and represent a geographically distributed group of users. The
443 RAs are required to adopt QARTOD QC standards to obtain Regional Coastal Observing Systems
444 (RCOS) certification.

445 **What is the maturity of QARTOD Quality Control for Real-Time Water Levels**

446 For this example, the real-time water level QC (RT WL QC) is evaluated for its maturity level. The RT
447 WL QC manual (U.S. IOOS, 2021) was first created in 2014, updated in April 2016, and again in
448 March 2021. A total of 271 comments were logged from 33 individuals representing 20 institutions
449 who contributed to the manual.

450 Level 1-2: The initial RT WL QC manual exceeded Levels 1 and 2 upon publication.

451 Level 3: All QARTOD manuals satisfy Level 3 guidelines.

452 Level 4: Documented examples of institutions implementing the QARTOD RT WL QC manual
453 include:

- 454 1. In (UNESCO/IOC, 2020), the use of QARTOD WL QC tests is described for the Global Sea-
455 Level Observing System (GLOSS, 2024)
- 456 2. In (Hofmann and Healy, 2017), the authors describe using the RT WL QC manual for the
457 calculation of vessel dynamic under-keel clearance in Australian ports.
- 458 3. HoHonu, a commercial manufacturer of water level gauges (Hohonu, 2024). On their frequently
459 asked questions page they state “Processed QA/QC data - “Cleaned” data following QARTOD
460 methodologies, implemented over four years of collaboration with SECOORA, Axiom Data
461 Science, and NOAA CO-OPS”.

462 Regarding sufficient practice documentation, indeed the purpose of QARTOD manuals is to convey
463 standardized QC practices to the eleven U.S. IOOS regional association data managers. Collectively,
464 these data managers have used the QC manuals to create GitHub pages which further support
465 standardization.

466 All QARTOD manuals are posted on the U.S. IOOS web page (U.S IOOS Website, 2024), and reside
467 on both the NOAA Institutional Repository (NOAA repository, 2024) and the OBPS repository.
468 Because the QARTOD acronym is quite unique, an internet search using any engine makes the manuals
469 readily findable.

470 The process for updating all QARTOD manuals is described in the QARTOD project plan update
471 (U.S.Integrated Ocean Observing System, 2022a), and as previously noted, this has been conducted
472 twice for this manual. The format for the results of the QC tests (QC data flags) is described in (U.S
473 .Integrated Ocean Observing System, 2020), which adheres to the IOC standard described in
474 (Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission, 2013).

475 All documents in the NOAA Institutional Repository are required to be Section 508 (U.S. Access
476 Board, 2024) compliant. Section 508 compliance is a machine-readable U.S. standard designed to
477 enable disabled individuals equal access to documents. As of January 18, 2018, all government
478 documents posted online are required to be Section 508 compliant.

479 Level 5: QARTOD RT WL QC tests have been implemented by multiple international entities. The
480 manual focuses on quality control, a critical aspect of quality assessment, but the manual does not
481 address the very challenging determination of measurement uncertainty. Feedback is obtained through
482 quarterly QARTOD Board of Advisors meetings and broadly distributed requests for comments during
483 manual updates by the National Coordinator. These updates are either incremental (no change to QC
484 tests already implemented) or substantial updates (requested by the community and requiring changes
485 to an implemented test), as described in U.S. Integrated Ocean Observing System, 2022. Finally, the
486 purpose of the manual is in fact to train data managers in the activity of data quality control in real
487 time.

488 **4.4 Assessment of Endorsed Practices**

489 Interviews were done with the primary author of each of seven practices endorsed by GOOS/OBPS
490 and held in the Ocean Best Practices System Repository. See Table 4-4. All the practices had completed
491 the attributes of Levels 1, 2 and 3. As a result, they are not included in the table, and only Levels 4 and
492 5 are shown.

493 The interviews covered both practice maturity and the ease or difficulty of using the attributes in each
494 of the maturity levels. The assessment served as a way to see where there were gaps in the practice

495 capabilities that should be addressed in moving to a fully mature best practice (Level 5). Generally, the
496 endorsed practices included guidance in duplicating the practice, most of the time by experts and at
497 times by new users. This is understandable, for some of these practices, as there are technologies like
498 DNA applications in the GO-SHIP plankton endorsed practice that require expertise for their
499 implementation.

500 It is important to recognize that endorsement is not synonymous with being a mature best practice. The
501 endorsement criteria (Bushnell and Pearlman, 2024) and (Hermes, 2020) do not include all attributes
502 of a Level 5 mature practice. The differences are attributes such as continuous improvement and
503 training. Thus, to be mature, a practice must be endorsed. On the other hand, an endorsed practice may
504 not include all the attributes to be fully mature. In the interviews summarized in Table 4-4, these
505 differences are apparent.

506 The responses of the lead authors for their endorsed practice is given in table 4-4. According to the
507 scoring system of the maturity model, where credit can be given on the attribute of the next higher
508 level, all of the endorsed practices were at Level 4 “Better Practice”. There are several attributes in
509 Level 5 that are not addressed by most of the practices. These include guidelines and protocols for
510 continuous improvement, formal monitoring for implementation and documented training materials.
511 These are a foundation for sustaining and improving practices and are essential for a best practice.
512 During the interviews, many of the lead authors agreed that these elements are important and indicated
513 that, as a result of the interviews, they will be addressed in the next version of the practice. Setting such
514 goals for practices is one benefit of the maturity model.

515 **5 Summary and recommendations**

516 Whether the issue is climate, marine litter or productivity of aquaculture, practices are created and
517 evolve to observe and analyze conditions to support decision making. There are many practices in
518 ocean research and applications which are created to address a particular measurement for
519 understanding the ocean and coastal environment. Sometimes these practices align or are naturally
520 complementary. Sometimes there are different approaches for the same end goal. This presents a
521 problem for practitioners to decide which method to use as they engage in new projects or applications.

522 An important question is what is a good practice or, ultimately, what is a best practice?

523 To address these questions in a systematic way, a maturity model for ocean practices was developed.
524 The model is built upon the experience over the last four decades in creating maturity models for
525 systems and software. There are challenges in doing this, relating to the degree of generality or
526 specificity that is needed for a practical model. General models endure, useful for strategic guidance;
527 more detailed models are effective for assessing the exact status of maturity but may need to evolve
528 more often.

529 For oceans, a five level model was chosen to provide a balance between generality and specificity. The
530 model has detailed attributes at each level to make the assessment more quantitative. In addition, the
531 attributes identify actions needed to move toward higher levels of maturity. In the process, the model
532 addresses both the maturity of the practice description (documentation) and maturity of its
533 implementation. The implementation maturity and, in particular, the sustainability and evolution of the
534 practice are generally not addressed by experts and yet are essential to foster regional and global
535 interoperability of practices.

536 The model was tested against practices with widespread adoption, some of which were also formally
 537 endorsed using a GOOS/OBPS endorsement process. In this testing, it was observed that a number of
 538 Level 5 attributes were not satisfied. These relate to sustainment and evolution of the practice. In testing
 539 practices with reference to the maturity model, practice authors agreed that there are gaps in their
 540 practice attributes and that the model was very useful in defining next steps for upgrading the practice
 541 to a best practice.

542 Propagating the maturity model to encourage widespread use is needed and will be done through
 543 incorporation of the model by various organizations as they guide ocean research and applications.
 544 Additional attributes for the model are under study. One question is whether there should be an attribute
 545 in the maturity matrix to credit a practice that is usable for a wide range of stakeholders with different
 546 resource availability. OBPS has a task team to address this, looking at applicability of practices in
 547 regions with limited human or infrastructure resources. This is important. The challenge is to define
 548 quantitative criteria to measure this attribute on a global scale. It is anticipated that this topic and others
 549 will be addressed in the next evolution of the maturity model.

550 In summary, the maturity model can identify key gaps in the evolution of a practice. It provides a
 551 definition for good, better, and best practices. The maturity model is a “living” concept which is
 552 expected to evolve over time. The work here provides a necessary foundation for widespread dialog
 553 on maturing and globalizing practices to support understanding processes, interoperability, and trust.

554 **6 Glossary**

Convergence	Agreement on a recommendation for a common practice in the selected areas
Endorsement	To approve openly, to express support or approval of publicly and, definitely, to recommend.
Harmonization	Practices which improve the comparability of variables from separate studies, permitting the pooling of data collected in different ways, and reducing study heterogeneity.
Interoperability	The ability of two or more systems to exchange and mutually use data, metadata, information, or system parameters using established protocols or standards. Involves standardizing technologies, data and analysis methods to facilitate collaboration and information sharing among various stakeholders in the ocean community.
Maturity	Mature process or technology is one that has been in use for long enough that most of its initial faults and inherent problems have been removed or reduced by further development.

Maturity level	A measure describing the state of development or readiness of a practice.
Metadata	Data that describes other data. Meta is a prefix that in most information technology usages means “an underlying definition or description.” Metadata summarizes basic information about data, which can make finding and working with particular instances of data easier; metadata may also be applied to descriptions of methodologies
NOAA Institutional Repository	a digital library of scientific literature and research produced by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (https://repository.library.noaa.gov/)
Ocean Observation/ Observing	Sustained observations of the ocean to understand climate change, predict weather and extreme events, to monitor ocean health, to support nations sustainable and blue economic growth, and adaptation to climate change. Data from ocean observing supports good policy and provides an evidence base for real-time decision-making, tracking the effectiveness of management actions, guiding adaptive responses to sustainable development, and supports businesses and jobs in the marine economy
Practice	A series of tasks executed in a specific order for achieving a specific outcome
Practice documentation (document) or practice description	The documented representation of all the tasks and activities the practice is made of, plus other comments and considerations useful to understand and disseminate and hopefully replicate the practice.
Quality Assurance/ Quality Control (QA/QC)	QA focuses on preventing defects or errors in the processes used to develop products. It is a proactive approach aimed at ensuring that the processes are designed and implemented effectively to produce high-quality products. QC involves the identification and correction of defects or errors in the finished products. It is a reactive approach focused on inspecting the products to ensure that they meet the specified quality standards. QC is traditionally part of QA.
Standardization	Process of developing, promoting and possibly mandating standards-based and compatible technologies and processes
Sustainability (of a	The practice has all the elements needed to be maintained over time

practice)	
Uncertainty (of measurement)	Parameter, associated with the result of a measurement, that characterizes the dispersion of the values that could reasonably be attributed to the measurand (BIPM 2008, see JCGM GUM 2008)
Value chain	The set of value-adding activities that one or more organizations perform in creating and distributing goods and services. In terms of ocean observing, the value chain approach can be applied to consider societal benefits of observations, data, analyses and assess the value of data and information features

555

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777 **8 Figures**

778 Figure 2-1. Five levels of the Capability Maturity Model, adapted from (Lutkevich, 2024)

779 Figure 3-1. Five Levels of Ocean Practice Maturity Model

780 Figure 4-1. The flawed data disseminated in real-time on October 02, 2015, are associated with a
 781 storm surge which brought water levels too close to the acoustic sensor. The abrupt shift seen shortly
 782 after 16:00 on 10/02/15 is the result of shifting to an alternative sensor at this site.

783 **9 Tables**

784 **Table 2-1.** Benefits and Challenges in Using Practices Maturity Models

Benefits
The path to maturity and a best practice is clearly documented
Gaps in documentation and capabilities are identified and can be addressed
Maturity structure supports monitoring of implementation, evolution and sustainability of practices
Users are aware of the practice maturity in selecting a practice for adoption
Practices can be compared according to selected criteria
Transparency increases trust in adopting practices
Challenges
Maturity models can be static, a snapshot, and not be able to keep up with technology evolution (it would demand a regular review to evolve)

The path through each level may not be optimized.
Practices across disciplines can vary and a maturity model may not be appropriate for all practices
Maturity criteria may be defined that are subjective and not objective
Maturity model implementation may demand additional effort for which the cost/benefit may not be clear, nor the quantitative implementation costs and infrastructure/human requirements
Independent organization may be required to assess maturity criteria that are subjective
Widespread recognition and adoption of the maturity model

785

786 **Table 3-1.** The five levels of maturity for ocean practices and the attributes required to reach a level. Score increment
787 shown is used for quantifying maturity level. A more detailed description is provided for some terms used in this table.

Level		Description of items to achieve the level
1	Formation of Practice	1.1 Practice is ad hoc with little documentation.
2	Emerging Practice - Repeatable	2.1 Practice is defined and may be documented. (.50) 2.2 Practice is repeatable by the practice creator. (.50) <i>Each of the above provides a score increment toward Level 2. Items from Level 2 and 3 may be used to achieve Level 2.</i>
3	Good Practice - Defined and documented	3.1 Practice is formally documented and supported by searchable metadata. (.30) 3.2 Practice documentation is openly available in a sustained repository with a DOI. (.30) 3.3 Practice documentation is sufficient for the practice to be replicated by practitioners with prior knowledge in similar practices. (.30) 3.4 Practice document formats and metadata conform at least to some existing guidelines. (.10)

		<p><i>Each of the above attributes provides a score increment toward Level 3. Items from Level 3 and 4 may be used to achieve Level 3. All items in Level 2 will have to be completed prior to achieving Level 3.</i></p>
4	Better Practice - Developed and Adopted	<p>4.1 Practice is recognized and actively used by multiple institutions but not necessarily formally endorsed. (.25)</p> <p>4.2 Practice document describes either explicitly or implicitly how practitioners can verify their successful implementation of the practice. (.20)</p> <p>4.3 Practice documentation is sufficient for the practice to be replicated by users without prior knowledge of similar practices (.20)</p> <p>4.4 Guidelines are available for evolution of practice and its documentation, such as updates or reviews and also have procedures for user feedback. (.20)</p> <p>4.5 Practice documentation has standardized formats and comprehensive metadata conforming to OBPS or other global standards (.10)</p> <p>4.6 Practice documents and metadata are machine-readable (.05)</p> <p><i>Each of the above attributes provides a score increment toward Level 4. Attributes from Level 4 and 5 may be used to achieve Level 4. All items in Level 3 will have to be completed prior to being at Level 4.</i></p>
5	Best Practice - Mature	<p>5.1 Practice is reviewed and endorsed by a multi-institutional expert panel following OBPS/GOOS endorsement protocols. (.35)</p> <p>5.2 Practice is adopted at least regionally. (.20)</p> <p>5.3 Practice includes process for quality assessment. (.15)</p> <p>5.4 Practice has specific protocols for supporting improvements including user feedback loops. (.10)</p> <p>5.5 Implementation of practice has formal tools (such as checklists, software checkers, assessment procedure, etc.) to verify implementation. (.10)</p> <p>5.6 Practice has materials for training (either described in the practice document or in a separate linked document(s)). (.10)</p> <p><i>Each of the above attributes provides a score increment toward Level 5. All items in both 4 and 5 must be satisfied for practice to be at Level 5</i></p>
<p>Definitions</p> <p>DOI: A DOI is a permanent digital identifier of an object, any object — physical, digital, or abstract. A DOI is a unique number made up of a prefix and a suffix separated by a forward slash.</p>		

DOIs identify objects persistently. They allow things to be uniquely identified and accessed reliably. (<https://www.doi.org/the-identifier/what-is-a-doi/>).

Feedback loop: e.g., a collaborative environment, with tracking capabilities for versions, comments, users (with authentication), where everyone can read comments from everyone. Not necessarily built by practice authors, it could be a third-party tool enabled by practice authors for this purpose.

Formal monitoring tools: tools for tracking and self-assessment, primarily for practitioners, but useful also for others.

Machine-readable: Product output that is in a structured format, which can be consumed by a computer program using consistent processing logic. For example, a PDF file is machine readable if it has either been computer generated or run through an OCR converter to convert it from a scanned PDF to searchable PDF.

OBPS: Ocean Best Practices System (<https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/>).

Quality assessment: QA focuses on preventing defects or errors in the processes used to develop products. It is a proactive approach aimed at ensuring that the processes are designed and implemented effectively to produce high-quality products.

Searchable metadata: the type of metadata that allows content to be found by a search phrase that has been used to describe the content in the metadata fields.

Standardized formats: referring to standardized formats and metadata conforming to OBPS document templates, see Ocean Best Practices System (2023).

Sustained repository: a permanent repository that has continuing funding and strategies in place for submissions, data curation, preservation, and dissemination to ensure that the stored information remains relevant, reliable, and accessible over time.

788

789 **Table 3-2.** Example of scoring in the maturity mode. ✓ = complies with attribute; X = does not satisfy this attribute. The
 790 analysis represents 2 full stars (Levels 1 and 2 completed), and two half stars (Levels 3 and 4 only partially fulfilled) and
 791 gives an overall score of 3.05.

Comply	score	Level 3
✓	.30	3.1 Practice is formally documented and supported by searchable metadata.
✓	.30	3.2 Practice is openly available in a sustained repository with a DOI.

X	.30	3.3 Practice documentation is sufficient for the practice to be replicated by practitioners with prior knowledge in similar practices.
✓	.10	3.4 Practice document formats and metadata conform at least to local guidelines.
	.70	Total for Level 3
		Level 4
X	.25	4.1 Practice is recognized and actively used by multiple institutions but not formally endorsed.
✓	.20	4.2 Practice document describes either explicitly or implicitly how practitioners can verify their successful implementation of the practice.
X	.20	4.3 Practice documentation is sufficient for the practice to be replicated by users without prior knowledge of similar practices.
X	.20	4.4 Guidelines are available for evolution of practice and its documentation, such as updates or reviews and also have procedures for user feedback.
✓	.10	4.5 Practice documentation has standardized formats and metadata conforming to OBPS or other global standards.
✓	.05	4.6 Practice documents and metadata are machine-readable.
	.35	Total for level 4
	1.05	Overall score for Level 3 acknowledgement (>=1.00 means practice is at Level 3)
	3.05	Overall score
		Overall stars ★★★★★

792

793 **Table 4-1.** Maturity assessment of HFR practices.

	<p>Recommendation Report 2 on improved common procedures for HFR QC analysis, JERICO-NEXT Deliverable 5.14, Version 2.0.</p> <p>Subject of the practice: near real time data quality control methods, data and metadata model implementation methods, for High Frequency Radar derived surface current.</p> <p>Material available: manual, software tools.</p>			<p>Quality Control procedures for IMOS Ocean Radar Manual, Version 3.0.</p> <p>Subject of the practice: data quality control methods for near-real time and delayed mode products, data formats, metadata, for High Frequency Radar derived surface current.</p> <p>Material available manual (updated).</p>		
attribute	comply	score	comments	comply	score	comments
Level 4						
4.1 Practice is recognized and actively used by multiple institutions but not necessarily formally endorsed.	✓	.25	Yes. recognized by JERICO partners, EuroGOOS, SeaDataNet partners, Copernicus In Situ TAC partners, Emodnet Physics. Employed by multiple institutions through the EU HFR node services.	✓	.25	Yes.
4.2 Practice document describes either explicitly or implicitly how practitioners can verify their successful implementation of the practice.	✓	.20	Yes, the practice documentation contains explicit description of means to verify the implementation. A formal verification can be performed at the EU HFR Node level for assessing the compliance with the data and metadata model suggested by the practice.	✓	.20	Yes, as formal evaluation (i.e. CF compliance) and assessment are done and documented.
4.3 Practice documentation is sufficient for the practice to be replicated by users without prior knowledge of similar practices	✓	.20	Yes, it relies on common statistical approach for data quality control, and refers to accepted standards for environmental data formats and metadata vocabularies.	✓	.20	Yes, commonly used statistical tests are implemented along with platform specific tests that require access to low level files in proprietary format.
4.4 Guidelines are available for evolution of practice and its documentation, such as updates or reviews and also have procedures for user feedback.	✓	.20	Yes. The process of reviewing the practice and its documentation is coordinated by the EuroGOOS HFR Task Team. The practice documentation is published on GitHub for user feedback, support and troubleshooting.	✓	.20	A periodic review process is coordinated by IMOS Community Practices and AODN, then submitted to Ocean Best Practices.

4.5 Practice documentation has standardized formats and comprehensive metadata conforming to OBPS or other global standards.	✓	.10	Practice documentation follows the structure provided by the OBPS data management template (for the data model sub-section).	✓	.10	Yes, OBPS format.
4.6 Practice documents and metadata are machine-readable.	✓	.05	Document is in a computer-generated PDF format.	✓	.05	Document is in a computer-generated PDF/A format.
Total for level 4		1.00			1.00	
Level 5						
5.1 Practice is reviewed and endorsed by a multi-institutional expert panel following OBPS/GOOS endorsement protocols.	✗	.35	No.	✗		No.
5.2 Practice is adopted at least regionally.	✓	.20	Yes, it represents the European data and metadata model and is adopted by multiple European Institutions (see 4.1).	✓	.20	Yes, as the Facility acts as a single data supplier for the entire Australia.
5.3 Practice includes process for quality assessment.	✓	.15	Yes, it includes algorithms for data QC.	✓	.15	Yes.
5.4 Practice has specific protocols for supporting improvements including user feedback loops.	✓	.10	Yes, the practice is also published on GitHub for providing user feedback loop, support and troubleshooting.	✓	.10	Registration of data users.
5.5 Implementation of practice has formal tools (such as checklists, software checkers, assessment procedure, etc.) to verify implementation.	✓	.10	Yes, software tools are publicly available on GitHub and Zenodo repositories for implementing the practice.	✓	.10	Yes, automatic CF compliance checkers available as standard AODN practice.
5.6 Practice has materials for training (either described in the practice	✓	.10	Yes, the training sessions and related material are managed by the	✓	.10	Yes, although not managed directly by the Facility and

document or in a separate linked document(s)			EuroGOOS HFR Task Team.			managed by AODN instead.
Total for Level 5		.65			.65	
Overall score		4.65			4.65	
Overall stars						

794

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Table 4-2. Maturity assessment of Multibeam practice

Comply	Score	Level 4	Comments
	.25	4.1 Practice is recognized and actively used by multiple institutions but not necessarily formally endorsed.	Multiple institutions use these guidelines, including government and national research agencies
	.20	4.2 Practice document describes either explicitly or implicitly how practitioners can verify their successful implementation of the practice.	Practice is part of a suite of marine sampling practices that describe how to appropriately cite and confirm implementation.
	.20	4.3 Practice documentation is sufficient for the practice to be replicated by users without prior knowledge of similar practices.	The nature of the practice requires technical specialization and complex and expensive equipment, but the documentation is as clear and detailed as possible for non-experts.
	.20	4.4 Guidelines are available for evolution of practice and its documentation, such as updates or reviews and also have procedures for user feedback.	Practice is part of a suite of marine sampling practices that have version control and maintenance plans. User feedback is solicited through an online form. Practice is part of a suite of marine sampling practices that describe how to appropriately cite and confirm implementation.
	.10	4.5 Practice documentation has standardized formats and comprehensive metadata conforming to OBPS or other global standards.	Appendix H in the practice (Picard et al 2020) details the required metadata in line with International Hydrographic Org.

✓	.05	4.6 Practice documents and metadata are machine-readable.	Document is presented in two forms, both machine readable: 1) standard pdf, 2) webpage (GitHub).
	1.0	Total for Level 4	
		Level 5	
X	.35	5.1 Practice is reviewed and endorsed by a multi-institutional expert panel following OBPS/GOOS endorsement protocols.	Endorsement has not yet been received as of March 2024, awaiting OBPS endorsement process
✓	.20	5.2 Practice is adopted at least regionally.	Practice has one of the highest uptakes for all Australian marine sampling practices (Przeslawski et al., 2021)
✓	.15	5.3 Practice includes process for quality assessment.	Included in section 'Quality assessment / uncertainty scheme' (Github - AusSeabed, 2024)
✓	.10	5.4 Practice has specific protocols for supporting improvements including user feedback loops.	Practice is managed through government initiative AusSeabed and is also part of a suite of marine sampling practices (Github - Field Manuals, 2024) that have version control and maintenance plans. User feedback is solicited through an online form.
✓	.10	5.5 Implementation of practice has formal tools (such as checklists, software checkers, assessment procedure, etc.) to verify implementation.	Uptake is measure through citations and google analytics via AusSeabed and NESP Marine and Coastal Hub
✓	.10	5.6 Practice has materials for training (either described in the practice document or in a separate linked document(s))	Relevant training and information materials are managed through AusSeabed's resource webpage (AusSeabed, 2024).
	.65	Total for Level 5	
	4.65	Overall score	

		Overall stars 	
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796

797 **Table 4-3.** Maturity assessment of QARTOD Real-Time Water Level Quality Control practice

Comply	Score	Level 4	Comments
✓	.25	4.1 Practice is recognized and actively used by multiple institutions but not necessarily formally endorsed	Implemented by the Global Sea-Level Observing System (GOOS), a private engineering firm (OMC International) in Australia for dynamic under-keel clearance, and water level sensor manufacturer (HoHonu).
✓	.20	4.2 Practice document describes either explicitly or implicitly how practitioners can verify their successful implementation of the practice.	Each QC test description is accompanied by an example of the test.
✓	.20	4.3 Practice documentation is sufficient for the practice to be replicated by users without prior knowledge of similar practices	Manual is designed to train data managers how to implement QC.
✓	.20	4.4 Guidelines are available for evolution of practice and its documentation, such as updates or reviews and also have procedures for user feedback	Update procedures are described in the QARTOD Project Plan, which is itself updated every five years.
✓	.10	4.5 Practice documentation has standardized formats and comprehensive metadata conforming to OBPS or other global standards	QC data flag format matches IOC, 2013 flagging standard.
✓	.05	4.6 Practice documents and metadata are machine-readable	All NOAA repository documents required to be machine-readable (Section 508 compliance).
	1.0	Total for Level 4	

		Level 5	
✓	.35	5.1 Practice is reviewed and endorsed by a multi-institutional expert panel following OBPS/GOOS endorsement protocols.	Manual is endorsed by U.S. IOOS, which is an organization of multiple Regional Associations and has been submitted to OBPS to be identified as endorsed in the repository.
✓	.20	5.2 Practice is adopted at least regionally	GLOSS, OMC International, Hohonu.
✓	.15	5.3 Practice includes process for quality assessment	The purpose of the manual is to standardize real-time QC, a significant component of QA.
✓	.10	5.4 Practice has specific protocols supporting continuous improvement including user feedback loops	<p>Capabilities include:</p> <p>1) a designated QARTOD National Coordinator, 2) a QARTOD Board of Advisors, ~12 members meet quarterly, 3) a request in the manual to contact either of these to report usage of the practice, 4) an annual meeting of the U.S. IOOS Data Management & Cyberinfrastructure (DMAC), the designated target audience for QARTOD manuals, where any of the users are able to initiate discussions about any QARTOD issues.</p> <p>The update process is described in the QARTOD Project Plan, which is also updated every five years. The two RT QC WL manual updates were initiated by the National Coordinator, who solicited input from the reviewers of the previous manual versions.</p>
X	.10	5.5 Implementation of practice has formal tools (such as checklists, software checkers, assessment procedure, etc.) to verify implementation.	The QARTOD manual does not include implementation monitoring tools. IOOS regional associations self-report implementation. They are required to implement QARTOD QC.
✓	.10	5.6 Practice has materials for training (either described in the practice document or in a separate linked document(s))	RT WL QC manual is the training material.
	.90	Total for Level 5	

	4.90	Overall score	
		Overall stars 	

798

799 **Table 4-4.** Overview of endorsed practice assessment by practices lead authors. In the table, **V** means a practice complies
800 with the attribute, **X** means a practice does not comply with the attribute (**X*** - a new version will be published soon which
801 is compliant in this area), and **?** means there is not sufficient information to determine compliance. Since the interviews,
802 the maturity model was refined to clarify the attributes.

Level 4	Core Argo Floats (Morris et al., 2023)	OOI BG (Palevsky et al., 2023)	Glider Oxygen (Lopez-Garcia et al., 2022)	GO-SHIP Nutrient (Becker et al., 2020)	GO-SHIP Plankton (Boss et al., 2020)	Baited Remote Survey (Langlois et al., 2020)	XBT QA Practices (Parks et al., 2021)
4.1 Practice is recognized and actively used by multiple institutions but not necessarily formally endorsed. (.25)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
4.2 Practice document describes either explicitly or implicitly how practitioners can verify their successful implementation of the practice. (.20)	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	X*	✓
4.3 Practice documentation is sufficient for the practice to be replicated by users without prior knowledge of similar practices (.20)	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓
4.4 Guidelines are available for evolution of practice and its documentation, such as updates or reviews and also have procedures for user feedback. (.20)	X	✓	✓	X	X	✓	✓
4.5 Practice documentation has standardized formats and comprehensive metadata conforming to OBPS or other global standards (.10)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
4.6 Practice documents and metadata are machine-readable (.05)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Total for Level 4	.80	.80	1.00	.80	.60	.80	1.00

Level 5	Core Argo Floats (Morris et al., 2023)	OOI BG (Palevsky et al., 2023)	Glider Oxygen (Lopez-García et al., 2022)	GO-SHIP Nutrient (Becker et al., 2020)	GO-SHIP Plankton (Boss et al., 2020)	Baited Remote Survey (Langlois et al., 2020)	XBT QA Practices (Parks et al., 2021)
5.1 Practice is reviewed and endorsed by a multi-institutional expert panel following OBPS/GOOS endorsement protocols.. (.35)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
5.2 Practice is adopted at least regionally (.20)	✓	✓	?	✓	✓	✓	✓
5.3 Practice includes process for quality assessment. (.15)	✓	✓	?	✓	✓	X*	✓
5.4 Practice has specific protocols for supporting improvements including user feedback loops. (.10)	X	✓	X	X*	?	✓	X
5.5 Implementation of practice has formal tools (such as checklists, software checkers, assessment procedure, etc.) to verify implementation. (.10)	✓	?	X	✓	?	X*	X
5.6 Practice has materials for training (either described in the practice document or in a separate linked document(s) (.10)	✓	✓	X	✓	?	X*	✓
Total for level 5	.90	.90	.35	.90	.70	.65	.80
Overall score	4.70	4.70	4.35	4.70	4.30	4.45	4.80
Overall stars	(Morris et al., 2023), (Palevsky et al., 2023), (Becker et al., 2020), (Boss et al., 2020), (Langlois et al.; 2020) ★★☆☆☆						
	(Lopez-García et al., 2022), (Parks et al., 2021) ★★★★★						

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